

THRESHOLD OF OVERALL ACCEPTABILITY FOR EBA QUALITY AND IDENTIFICATION OF NEW CLONES THAT MEET THE THRESHOLD

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for high-quality cassava necessitates breeding programs to focus on improving the sensory, textural, and color attributes of eba. To guide these breeding efforts, understanding the acceptability thresholds for key quality parameters is crucial. By establishing clear sensory thresholds based on consumer preferences and descriptive sensory analysis, researchers can define the acceptable range for each quality trait. Additionally, translating these sensory thresholds into objective instrumental measurements will enable more efficient and cost-effective screening of candidate clones. By incorporating these components into breeding programs, researchers can accelerate the development of cassava varieties that consistently meet consumer expectations.

Nineteen (19) diverse cassava genotypes were harvested during the 2020-2023 planting season at the field plots of International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ikenne station. The genotypes were established in a randomized complete block design with two replications and harvested 12 months after planting. The harvested cassava was processed into gari and eba for further sensory evaluation and consumer preference tests. To assess consumer preferences, a "Just-About-Right" (JAR) scale with three points was used to evaluate colour, firmness, and stickiness. A total of 120 consumers were surveyed at the IITA staff canteen in October 2022. A quantitative descriptive analysis (QDA) was conducted by a trained panel of fifteen (15) individuals. Findings show that the threshold of acceptability for the color of gari ranges from **2.4 to 3.2**, and optimum acceptability was **2.9** and R^2 of 0.53, while the acceptability threshold for the Eba hardness ranges from **200 to 400 N**, with optimum acceptability at **300 N**.

Key Words: Cassava roots, sensory, consumer testing, texture, threshold of acceptability

1 METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out following the RTBfoods' Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00596>), (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00604>). The consumer preferences (JAR) for colour, firmness, and stickiness were visualized using ggplot2. The acceptability thresholds for each attribute were estimated using a quadratic regression model implemented in R, following the methodology proposed by Zoé et al. (2024) (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00777>).

In the 2020-2023 planting season, an experimental trial was conducted at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) research station in Ikenne to evaluate 19 diverse, white-fleshed cassava genotypes using 511 consumers. These genotypes were established in a randomized complete block design with two replications and harvested 12 months after planting.

2 FINDINGS

2.1 Distribution of consumer preference

The Just-About-Right (JAR) data collected from consumers provided critical insights into their preferences for sensory traits across the tested cassava varieties. In terms of color (Figure 1A), consumers rated SIMONYE as having the highest percentage (83 %) of "Just About Right" ratings, indicating its strong appeal for this trait. However, IITA-TMS-IBA071313 was predominantly perceived as too dark, with 86 % of consumers rating it as such, suggesting a potential need for improvement in its visual appeal.

In terms of firmness (Figure 1B), IITA-TMS-IBA990304 was judged as "Too Soft" by 63 % of consumers, whereas IITA-TMS-IBA090576 was considered "Too Firm" by 51 %. These findings suggest that adjustments in texture are necessary to better align these varieties with consumer preferences.

For stickiness (Figure 1C), IITA-TMS-ZAR010116 was considered to have the ideal texture, receiving the highest proportion (66 %) of "Just About Right" ratings. In contrast, genotype IITA-TMS-IBA090576 was regarded as "Not Sticky Enough" by 57 % of consumers, highlighting a preference for increased stickiness in this variety. Additionally, genotype TMEB693 was most frequently rated as "Just About Right" (79 %), making it the preferred texture in this category.

A

B

C

Figure 1: Distribution of consumer preference

2.2 Threshold of Traits Acceptability

2.2.1 Colour Acceptability Threshold

The thresholds for overall acceptability of colour of eba using JAR and QDA values. Based on **Figure 2**, the QDA scores corresponded to 75% and 65% consumer satisfaction, a high level of acceptability, ranging from **2.4 to 3.2** and optimum acceptability was **2.9** with an R^2 of 0.53. These thresholds indicate that a product with a QDA score between 2.4 and 3.2 will be perceived as highly acceptable by up to 75 % most consumers, though with scores outside the range of 2.4 to 3.2 are likely to result in dissatisfaction, suggesting that the product's colour deviates too far from what consumers consider acceptable.

Figure 2 : Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) for colour,

2.2.2 Hardness Acceptability Threshold

The thresholds for the overall acceptability of eba hardness were determined using JAR, QDA, and ITPA hardness values (Figure 3a). Based on Figure 3, the ITPA hardness scores correspond to 65% and 60% consumer satisfaction had an R^2 value of 0.18. A high level of acceptability was observed within the range of **200 to 400 N**, with optimum acceptability at **300 N**. These thresholds indicate that a product with an ITPA hardness score between 200 and 400 N will be perceived as highly acceptable by up to 65 % of consumers. However, scores outside this range are likely to result in dissatisfaction, signaling that the product's hardness deviates too far from consumer preferences. Also, the acceptability threshold for QDA hardness ranged from **3.5 to 6.0** with an optimum value of **4.75** (Figure 3b).

Figure 3a: Instrumental measurement of hardness of eba.

Figure 3b: Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) for hardness,

2.3 Selection of 3 genotypes using the threshold of Acceptability for the selected traits

Based on the threshold of acceptability of colour and firmness (QDA and ITPA), genotypes TMS13F1343P0002, TMS13F1088P0007, and TMS13F1053P0010 (Table 1) fall within the established acceptability thresholds for these traits. This means that these genotypes meet consumer acceptability thresholds for colour and firmness based on the QDA and ITPA measurements.

Table 1 : Genotypes that meet the threshold of acceptability

Sensory attribute	Colour	Firmness_ITPA	Firmness_QDA
TTMS13F1343P0002	2.8	296.6	3.0
TMS13F1088P0007	3.1	313.4	3.7
TMS13F1053P0010	2.5	258.9	3.0

3. CONCLUSION

The threshold of acceptability for the target quality parameters for gari and Eba has been defined using the “JAR” test, Quantitative descriptive analysis and instrumental texture measurements using 19 diverse cassava genotypes. The findings from the study have shown that the threshold of acceptability for the colour of gari ranges from 2.4 to 3.2. The optimum acceptability was 2.9, and R2 of 0.53. In contrast, the acceptability threshold for the Eba hardness ranges from 200 to 400 N, with optimum acceptability at 300 N. Therefore, researchers can use these threshold limits as a selection index for the consumer-preferred quality traits for the product profile.

APPENDICES

Annex 1: Threshold of acceptability using % of unsatisfied consumers for color

Calculation of Thresholds using % unsatisfied consumers

Annex 2: Threshold of acceptability using % of unsatisfied consumers for hardness

Calculation of Thresholds using % unsatisfied consumers